

OUTCOMES OF PERCUTANEOUS NEPHROLITHOTOMY AND OPEN PYELOLITHOTOMY IN THE MANAGEMENT OF RENAL STONES >2CM

Dr Amir Zeb Khan^{*1}, Dr Muhammad Asif², Dr Muhammad Usman³, Dr Hamza Khan⁴

^{*1,3,4}Resident Urologist, Department of Urology, MTI/LRH, Peshawar, Pakistan.

²Associate Professor, Department of Urology, MTI/LRH, Peshawar, Pakistan

¹aamirwazir12@gmail.com, ²drasif_14@yahoo.com,
³innocent_member99@yahoo.com, ⁴03169743024@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Amir Zeb Khan

Abstract

Background: Renal stones are one of the main urological concerns and one of the main cause of urinary tract infections. Due to its increasing prevalence in recent era the management modalities have shifted from open urological procedures to endourological procedure with minimal trauma to the tissues. However the option between open vs percutaneous nephrolithotomy is still debatable for optimal patient outcome.

Aim: The aim of the study is to compare the outcome of open pyelolithotomy and Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy and provide the valuable insight for treatment decision.

Method: This 06 months randomized control trials conducted in tertiary care hospital in which 134 patients being allocated randomly to both groups and standardized procedure being performed. Stone free status will confirmed on ultrasound and other outcomes will be assessed postoperatively between the two groups.

Results: This study compared open pyelolithotomy and percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) for renal stone management, showing similar stone clearance rates (92.5% vs 85.1%, $p=0.178$). However, PCNL had significantly less hemoglobin drop, shorter hospital stay, and operative time compared to open pyelolithotomy ($p<0.001$).

Conclusions:

PCNL is better due to shorter hospital stays and less blood loss, making it useful for patients with comorbidities. Open pyelolithotomy may still be preferred for complex stones or anatomical abnormalities.

INTRODUCTION

The incidence of kidney stones is rising globally. Kidney stones are usually the solid mineral deposits typically made of calcium, oxalate and phosphate, they usually imbalances the urinary composition and eventually pass out through urethra in the form of concentrate urine¹. Kidney stones are the third most

common urinary tract problem after urinary tract infections and prostate disorders. Kidney stones are classified into calcium oxalate, Calcium phosphate, uric acid, cysteine, struvite, and mixed stones types each of which releases specific substances in urine.

Calcium stones accounts for almost 70-80% of all kidney stones².

Kidney stones risk factors differs among different population groups. Environmental factors, diet, ethnic group, genetics, lifestyle all these factors play key role in their pathogenesis³. Study on urological patients has revealed that there is an association between the following factors as mentioned to the development of kidney stone i.e. sex, race, geographic region, occupation, hot climate, positive family history, unhealthy diet (excessive intake of caffeine, salt, dairy products, animal proteins and fat), smoking, alcohol consumption, physical activity, obesity, low fluid intake, dehydration socioeconomic status, education, water quality, high intake of vitamins D and C, genetic background and comorbid metabolic disorders, diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, chronic kidney disease and cardiovascular disease)⁴.

With the advances in shock wave lithotripsy (SWL) and end urological procedures such as percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) and ureterorenoscopy (URS), the treatment of urinary stone disease has changed markedly. The indications for open renal surgery to treat renal calculi are limited to special situations; it is needed in only 0.47% to 5.4% of the time. According to the guidelines Open pyelolithotomy is indicated when endoscopic procedures fail, if there is a complex stone burden, renal and anatomical abnormalities⁵. In a study by Aroinsharifi et al, On average, 95.34% of the stone burden was cleared by one-session of open AN, whereas PCNL cleared 81.61% of the stone burden in one-session⁶.

In the present study the outcome of percutaneous nephrolithotomy and open pyelolithotomy for the management of patients with renal stone will be analyzed. This will be the first of its kind study that will specifically focus on the clinical efficacy of these procedures in head to head comparison. Results of the study will help in better understanding of various procedures performed for renal stones in our local population. It will also help in better counselling of such patients.

Objective:

To compare the outcomes of percutaneous nephrolithotomy and open pyelolithotomy in the management of renal stones.

Operational Definitions:

Renal stones: It will be confirmed on ultrasound abdomen revealing renal stone that fills >80 % of the corresponding collecting system.

Outcomes: will be in terms of stone free rate (SFR) which will be determined on ultrasound abdomen performed 24hours after surgery. SFR will be defined as absence or renal stone fragments sizing smaller than 4mm.

Hypothesis:

Open pyelolithotomy has better outcomes (stone free rate) than percutaneous nephrolithotomy in patients with renal stones.

Materials and Methodology:

Study design:

Randomized controlled trail

Settings:

Department of Urology, MTI/Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar

Study duration:

06 months after the approval of synopsis

Sample size:

Sample size is calculated using Open Epi software taking the following assumptions

Anticipated stone free rate with open pyelolithotomy = 95.3%⁶

Anticipated stone free rate percutaneous nephrolithotomy = 81.6%⁶

Power of test = 80%

Confidence

Level = 95%

Sample size, n = 134 (67 in each group)

Sampling technique:

Non probability consecutive sampling technique

Ethical Consideration:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Lady Reading Hospital Ref: no.201/LRH/MTI, written informed consent was obtained from all participants, with clear explanation of study objectives, voluntary participation, and right to withdraw. Patient consent was secured for observational components. Data confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study process

Sample Selection:

Inclusion criteria

- Patient age 18 to 60 years
- Both genders
- Diagnosed as renal stones as per operational definitions

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with previous history of intervention for renal stone in the same kidney
- Patients with previous history of ESWL in the same kidney
- Patients with solitary kidney
- Patients with active urinary tract infection
- Patients with creatinine more than 1.5mg/dl
- Patients with anatomical aberrations in the same kidney

Data Collection Procedure:

After taking approval from research review board of the hospital, patients fulfilling the selection criteria will be enrolled from the indoor department of the urology of the hospital. Informed consent will be taken from all enrolled participants after explaining the purpose, risks and benefits of the study. Baseline information and demographics like age (years), gender, laterality of the kidney (right/left), stone size (mm) and comorbidities like hypertension (BP > 140/90mmHg), diabetes (FBS >126mg/dl) will be recorded.

Patients will be assigned to group A and B through blocked randomization in equal number. Patients in group A will undergo open pyelolithotomy while patients in group B will undergo percutaneous nephrolithotomy. All patients will be admitted one day before their surgery and received light bowel preparation and intravenous Ceftriaxone (1 g every 12 h) so that sterility of the urine is ensured prior to the operation. All surgeries will be performed under general anesthesia by the same surgical team led consultant urologist with minimum 05 years post-fellowship experience and the researcher as assistant. Standard PCNL will be done under general anesthesia with the patient in the prone position. Percutaneous access to the lower calyx will be achieved under fluoroscopic guidance. The tract will be dilated up to 28 Fr and a 30-Fr Amplatz sheath will be placed. Pneumatic lithotripter will be used for stone

fragmentation and an 18-Fr nephrostomy tube will be placed in each tract after completion of the procedure. Open pyelolithotomy will be performed through a large retroperitoneal intercostal flank incision. After complete dissection of the renal pedicle the kidney will be mobilized within the Gerota fascia. The renal artery will be temporary clamped with an atraumatic bulldog clamp. The stone will be removed en bloc through a nephrotomy incision over the Brodel line (i.e., about 2 cm posterior to the lateral convex surface of the kidney). The nephrotomy incision will be closed with two rows of 2-0 polyglactin running sutures. After the bulldog clamp will be released, renal perfusion as well as any bleeding sites from the nephrotomy incision will be checked. Thirty minutes before ligation of the renal artery and after its release, 12.5 g mannitol will be infused. Standard post-operative care will be given to all patients comprising of adequate antibiotics coverage, analgesia, IV fluids and vitals monitoring. Stone free status will be confirmed on ultrasound abdomen performed the next day to record the outcomes as per operational definitions.

Data will be recorded by the researcher himself on especially designed proforma.

Data Analysis Procedure:

Data will be analyzed using statistical analysis program IBM SPSS version 25. Means \pm SD or will be recorded for quantitative data like age stone size after checking the normality of the data will Shapiro wilk test while frequencies and percentages will be recorded for qualitative data like gender, laterality of the stone, comorbidities and outcomes. Both groups will be compared for outcomes by applying chi square or fisher exact test at 5% level of significance. Post stratification chi square or fisher exact test will be applied. P value ≤ 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results:

A total of 134 patients were enrolled in the study, with 67 patients assigned to Group A, undergoing open pyelolithotomy. The demographic breakdown of Group A revealed a male-to-female ratio of 40 (59.7%) males and 27 (40.3%) females with the mean age of 45.6 years (SD = 10.2). While 67 patients were enrolled in Group B, undergoing percutaneous

Nephrolithotomy. The male to female ratio is 42(62.7%) males and 25(37.3%) females with the mean age of 44.9 years (SD = 11.1).

Laterality of stone in group 1 and 2 were described in the figure below

Figure.01 Laterality of stone Group A

Figure.02 Laterality of stone Group B

Mean drop of hemoglobin, Hospital stay time, mean operative time and average stone size were also

compared between the two groups as shown in the table below.

Group. A	
Mean drop in Hemoglobin(Hb)	1.5 g/dL (SD = 0.5)
Hospital stay time	5.5 days (SD = 1.2)
Mean operative time	110min
Average stone size	3.2 cm (SD = 0.7)
Group. B	
Mean drop in Hemoglobin(Hb)	1g/dL (SD = 0.3)
Hospital stay time	3.2 days (SD = 0.9)
Mean operative time	85min
Average stone size	2.5 cm (SD = 0.6)

Table no.01 Comparison of Group A with B

Open pyelolithotomy resulted in complete stone clearance in 62 out of 67 patients, yielding a stone clearance rate of 92%. However, 5 patients (7.5%)

had residual stones greater than 4mm postoperatively, indicating a small proportion of patients required further intervention.

Figure.03 Open pyelolithotomy

While percutaneous nephrolithotomy resulted in stone clearance of 57 out of 67 patients with the clearance rate of 85% with 10 patients having

residual stone of greater than 4mm mimicking such patients may need further intervention postoperatively.

Figure.04 Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PCNL)

We'll compare the outcomes between Group A (Open Nephrolithotomy) with statistical level of significance. Pyelolithotomy) and Group B (Percutaneous

Group	Stone Clearance	Residual Stones	Total
A (Open)	62 (92.5%)	5 (7.5%)	67
B (PCNL)	57 (85.1%)	10 (14.9%)	67

Table.02 Stone clearance rate statistical significance

P-value: 0.178

The p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating no statistically significant difference in stone clearance rates between the two groups

Outcome	Group A (Open)	Group B (PCNL)	P-value
Mean drop in Hemoglobin (g/dL)	1.5 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.3	< 0.001
Hospital stay time (days)	5.5 ± 1.2	3.2 ± 0.9	< 0.001
Mean operative time (minutes)	110	85	< 0.001

Table.03 Outcome statistical significance

The p-values indicate statistically significant differences in hemoglobin drop, hospital stay time, and operative time between the two groups.

Discussion:

In this study we compared the stone clearance rate and other outcomes of patients undergoing open

pyelolithotomy with percutaneous nephrolithotomy. The relative percentage of stone clearance via Open pyelolithotomy vs PCNL (92.5% vs 82.1%) shows no statistical significance as $p = 0.178$. This suggests that both procedures have equal percentage of stone clearance but other outcomes between these two procedures shows statically significant results.

Our study found that patients undergoing open surgery had longer hospital stays and higher stone-free rates (SFR) postoperatively compared to those in the PCNL group, consistent with existing literature⁷. The stone clearance rate in both groups (Group A: 92.5%, Group B: 82.1%) achieved in our study were as per the literature^{8,9}. According to another study Stone clearance rate of 81.9% and 91.6% following PCNL and open surgery was achieved which also supports our study results⁷.

The mean drop of Hemoglobin, Hospital stay and longer operative time indicates the more invasive nature of open pyelolithotomy, these findings are also consistent with results of Matlaga et al.¹⁰. In contrast to our study in which PCNL group patients have more postoperative complications and bleeding requiring transfusion⁷. The mean drop in Hb following PCNL in our study was 1.0 ± 0.3 which is comparable to a study in which the loss was 0.97 ± 0.49 ¹¹.

PCNL though its stone clearance rate is almost equal to that of open procedure but its promising faster recovery, shorter hospital stay and less drop of hemoglobin is advantageous^{12,13}. PCNL is comparatively better option for patients having co morbidities because its relative complications i.e. blood loss, hospital stay, operative time are less and hence postoperative recovery is faster so should be preferable¹⁴. The American Urological institute recommends PCNL as the primary preference for large renal stone¹⁵. Al-Kohlany et al. also recommends PCNL as a better option for staghorn calculi¹⁶.

The Higher clearance rate in Open pyelolithotomy though statistically not significant might be due to direct visualization and manipulation but this comes at the cost of potentially more complications and invasive nature of the procedure^{17,18}. Open surgery is currently used in less than 5% of the cases⁷. Open pyelolithotomy is preferable for selected patients having large complex stones, failed PCNL and for the restoration of anatomical abnormalities of collecting system¹⁹. Almost 2% of patients were treated by open

pyelolithotomy in US in 2000¹⁶. Open pyelolithotomy is still a better treatment for patients having anatomical abnormalities, pyuria, and complex stones¹⁶.

Conclusion:

Our study accomplishes that while both open pyelolithotomy and PCNL have almost similar stone clearance rates, PCNL offers preferable because of its shorter hospital stays and less blood loss. PCNL is advantageous for patients having co morbidities because of its less complications. Open pyelolithotomy may still be preferred for complex stones or patients having anatomical abnormalities. Overall, PCNL is a more favorable option due to its minimally invasive nature.

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

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